

Impact of Documented Information Planning and Efficient Delivery of an Organization's Goods and Services

Authored by

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Abstract

In this study, the impact of documented information on the planning and efficient delivery of an organization's goods and services was examined. In fact, the study summarily investigated the role of records management on efficient organizational performance. The objectives were to find out what the impact of records management is on general efficiency and cost and time management in organizations in the hope of evolving functional strategies for proper documented information management. The study used three companies as its case study organizations namely; TENG/PCNL in Port Harcourt metropolis, AOS in Port Harcourt metropolis and United Bank for Africa in Enugu metropolis. A sample of 92 respondents from these companies was used while the Chi-square statistical measurement method was also adopted. Of the three-hypothesis developed, only two were testable; the impact of record keeping and documented information management on organizational efficiency and impact of record keeping and management on cost and time saving. The test outcome confirmed at the 5% critical level that both hypotheses were statistically significant. Against the baseline statistical table reading value of 21, the first test reached an empirical value of 30.9 while the second reached a value of 27.2 both of which are greater than 21 leading to the rejection of the null hypotheses on both tests. The study concluded that there is need for a regulation on standard corporate record keeping and documented information management. It also recommended regular trainings and sufficient budgetary allocations to the record keeping expense head. It recommended that the government should evolve standard regulatory framework for documented information management while organizations should create standard documented information management policies in tune with known international standards such as ISO and API. It also recommended sufficient financial and resource budgets for the documented information, proper training for the line managers, digitization of the records management process and adequate supervision of the entire process.

Keywords: Documented Information Planning; Efficient Delivery; Organization's Goods and Services; Financial and Resource Budgets

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Introduction

Irrespective of type of activity and its size, no company can operate without documented information. From its scope of the quality management system, information necessary to support the operation of quality management system (QMS) processes, quality policy and the quality objectives to the most detailed work instructions, all important and useful information about the smooth operation of the company is documented. This information must be clear, precise and easily accessible by the employees concerned. It is also important that this documentation is up-to-date, incorporating the latest evolutions and modifications, while eliminating obsolete items. In summary, documents must be updated to be applicable (Molepo and Cloete, 2017).

The term "documented information" in ISO 9001 refers to all of the important information within a business that must be kept organized and controlled. It is basically a combination of documents and records. In previous versions of ISO standards, the terms "documents" and "records" were formally used to refer to the important information and data that exists within a company. In the current ISO 9001 guidelines these terms have changed, and been combined under the same category of "documented information" (ISO, 2015).

The documented information discussed in ISO 9001 is defined as the vital information that must be kept and evaluated periodically. Records are usually retained for long periods of time, while documents hold data that is maintained and frequently updated or added to. The quality management system (QMS) is a formalized system that documents processes, procedures, and responsibilities for achieving quality policies and objectives. A QMS helps coordinate and direct an organization's activities to meet customer and regulatory requirements and improve its effectiveness and efficiency on a continuous basis (ISO, 2016).

The international standard (ISO9001:2015) specifying requirements for quality management systems, is the most prominent approach to quality management systems. While some use the term "QMS" to describe the ISO 9001 standard or the group of documents detailing the QMS, it actually refers to the entirety of the system. The documents only serve to describe the system.

The following documented information is to be maintained by keeping it up-to-date and relevant to the QMS:

The scope which defines the boundaries that surround the QMS processes. These boundaries are reflective of which standard requirements apply to the organization and what parts of the processes will be included in the QMS. Also, the scope specifies any exclusion from the standard requirements with justification. This scope appears on the certificate that is issued by the Certification Body if the organization is certified to any of the quality management system standards like API or ISO. The scope of our quality management system applies to all products and services offered by the company including design, production and post-delivery activities. The relevant internal and external issues for the QMS and actions to address identified risks and found improvements opportunities are taken into account. The goals and purposes of the standard, the approach and reference to customer requirements, the approach and reference to regulatory or statutory requirements, applicability of the standard requirements (Abdul-Rahamon and Adejare, 2014). From a review of the nature of your business's operations, products and services, the scope of the management system should be apparent by the extent of the processes and controls that your organization has already established. The scope of your management system may include the whole of the organization, specific and identified functions within the organization, specific sections of the organization, or one or more functions across a group of organizations (ISO, 2015). Information to support the operations of QMS processes might include Audit Reports, Corrective Reports, Nonconformity/defect reports, management review records, inspections and monitoring records. The quality policy and the quality objectives display the information about the processes of the company regarding how they are currently running and how they will run in the future. The records portion of the documented information, on the other hand, is very lengthy. With a total of 21 records that are required, this section of documented information gets into detail about almost every aspect of the business. Evidence of fitness for purpose of monitoring and measuring resources. Evidence of the basis used for calibration of the monitoring and measurement resources. Evidence of competence of people doing work under the control of the organization that affects the performance and effectiveness of the QMS. Documented information required by the QMS. Results of the review and requirements for the products and services. Records to demonstrate compliance with design and development requirements. customer requirements, the approach and reference to regulatory or statutory requirements, applicability of the standard requirements. Records of design and development inputs.

Records of the activities of design and development controls. Records of design and development outputs. Design and development changes, including the results of the review and the authorization of the changes and necessary actions. Records of the evaluation, selection, monitoring of performance and re-evaluation of external providers and any actions arising. Evidence of the unique identification of outputs when traceability is a requirement. Records of property of the customer or external provider that is lost, damaged or non-conforming and of its communication to the owner. Results of the review of changes for production or service provision, the persons authorizing the change, and necessary actions taken. Records of authorized release of products for delivery to the customer including acceptance criteria and traceability to the authorizing person(s). Records of non-conformities, actions taken, concessions and the identity of the authority deciding the action in respect of the nonconformity. Results of the evaluation of the performance and the effectiveness of the QMS. Evidence of the implementation of the audit program and the audit results. Evidence of the results of management reviews. Evidence of the nature of the nonconformities and any subsequent actions taken. Results of any corrective actions.

Reinhold and Carl (1963) believe that the secret behind many successful organizations could be largely found in their record keeping culture. Thus, this has become a defining character of most successful organization and any organization where records of transactions are not properly kept stand a real chance of collapsing. In order to be effective, efficient and competitive, all organizations keep records of their activities. By keeping such records accurately and up-to-date, organizations can measure their performance, improve their overall financial control and take action whenever problems arise (Hamouda, Mahmoud, 2013).

Modern information system has plunged the world into what may be called an information age as opposed to the book age (Akotia, 2011). Information is an essential resource for decision-making at international, national and even lower organizational levels of human activity. However, for information to be fully effective, it should be classified, recorded, and stored appropriately in an effective manner. This information is known as a record and the discipline in which record or information is captured, stored and managed in a meaningful format is the substance of records management. Records are therefore a vital tool in the administration of many organizations. The success and failure of organizations and state organs activities all depends on the efficient handling of information (Sajuyigbe et al, 2016).

There is no doubt that the information revolution, and the nature of communications and records management that the new world is witnessing has impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of work of organizations. where the work of many business organizations has switched from manual to computerized methods based on the use of computers and communication networks, databases and many other technological means to, process and analyze the data to get the output and the results have become precious information sanctuaries. So, it could well be figured that information storage either in soft or hard copy is very important in improving decision making. This has as well become a very critical administrative function which contributes to improving management performance in the quality of services provided by the Organization. With proper information storage and management, time, effort and cost are saved which lead to growth in profits.

Surprisingly, there has not been adequate literature on the importance of documented information. Researchers seem to be more interested in studying the dynamics and changing phases of the global information system and what drives this phenomenon but with relatively low interest in studying how it affects performance in the work place (Steemson, 2014). Therefore, in the light of the importance of documented information storage, this study intends to further examine how documentation of business facts and proper safe-keeping of such documents could influence the efficient delivery of goods and services. Put differently, this study intends to examine the influence of information documentation and storage on the organizational performance.

Materials and Methods

This study is designed as a survey study using a sample population of staff of TENG/PCNL (Port Harcourt Metropolis), AOS (Port Harcourt Metropolis), United Bank for Africa (Enugu metropolis) to seek understanding on the impact of documented information, records keeping and management on organizational efficiency. Port Harcourt is the capital of Rivers State, Nigeria and largest city in the state. Rivers state is located in southern Nigeria, comprising the Niger River delta on the Gulf of Guinea. It is bounded by the states of Anambra and Imo on the north, Abia and Akwa Ibom on the east, and Bayelsa and Delta on the west. Enugu State is one of the states in the eastern part of Nigeria located

at the foot of the Udi Plateau. The state shares borders with Abia State and Imo State to the south, Ebonyi State to the east, Benue State to the northeast, Kogi State to the northwest and Anambra State to the west. Enugu State is located on the North western fringe of south eastern Nigeria. The study is executed based on a simple structured questionnaire articulated based on its objectives.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing the study area (Source: NGS, 2015)

Sources of Data

The sources of data for this study consist of the responses from the respondents which formed the basis of the analysis and findings of the research. However, secondary data were also very relevant and consisted of already published data in books, journals, magazines, academic thesis and projects which formed the basis for the review of literature on the subject.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of the employees of the three branches of the selected banks as presented on table 1 below:

Table 1: Break down of the population according to the branches.

	TENG/PCNL		TOTAL
TENG OGFZ Onne 36	PCNL OGFZ Onne 46		82
	AOS		
Trans Amadi50	OGFZ Onne 21		71
	UBA		
Station Road 33	Otigba 27	Garki 24	84
TOTAL			237

Table 1 Break down of the population according to the organizations.

Determination of Sample Size

Having established the population of the study at 237, the researcher adopted the Taro Yemene finite population formula in determining the sample size. The formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N (0.05)^2} \quad (1)$$

n = Sample

N = Population

e = limit of tolerance error

thus we have for our overall sample size,

$$n = \frac{237}{1 + 237(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{237}{1 + 237(0.0025)}$$

$$n = 237 / 1.5925$$

n = 149

Therefore, our final sample size is 149

The author therefore adopted a proportional representation approach in the distribution of this final sample among the banks. The proportion of the companies to the final sample is determined as follows:

$$\text{TENG/PCNL: } 82/237 \times 100 = 34.6\%$$

$$\text{AOS: } 71/237 \times 100 = 30\%$$

$$\text{UBA: } 84/237 \times 100 = 35.4\%$$

As shown above, TENG/PCNL has 34.6% of the study population, AOS; 30% and UBA; 35.4%. Using this, we share the final sample of 149 as presented in table 3.3 below.

Table 2: Table showing proportion of final sample from each bank.

Bank	Number of employees	Number selected	Sample
TENG/PCNL	82	34.6/100 x 149	51
AOS	71	30/100 x 149	45
UBA	84	35.4/100 x 149	53
TOTAL	237		149

Source: Field survey 2022

From table 2. above, TENG/PCNL's contribution to the final sample size is 51, AOS's is 45 while that of UBA is 53. This is proportional to the original population of the three branches of each of the studied organizations from the origin.

Using the same proportional representation approach as above, we determine the proportion of the individual organization's sample that comes from each of the branches involved in the survey.

$$\text{TENG/PCNL: } 51/82 \times 100 = 62.2\%$$

$$\text{AOS: } 45/71 \times 100 = 63.4\%$$

$$\text{UBA: } 53/84 \times 100 = 63.1\%$$

Table 3. Break down of the sample according to the branches.

	Sample Selected	TENG/PCNL	Sample Selected	Sample Selected	TOTAL
TENG OGFZ Onne	22	PCNL OGFZ Onne	29		51
Trans Amadi	32	AOS OGFZ Onne	13		45
Station Road	21	UBA Otigba	17	Garki	53
GRAND TOTAL					149

Source: Field survey 2022

Instrument of the Study and Validation

The instrument of study was a simple and structured questionnaire, which was organized in a manner that addresses the key issues in the study objectives and research questions. The document is comprehensive and was made easy to understand by the respondents. The method of questioning used was the Likert's semantic differential such as Totally Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree and Totally Disagree.

The instrument was validated at two stages; first, the document was subjected to a small group of respondents called (pilot group) for completion. The responses of this group indicated that some propositions were not clear. Such propositions were dropped in the final questionnaire. Second, the instrument was submitted to an expert in research methods for vetting. More questions were dropped and some added. The final proposition was considered good to capture the purpose and objectives of the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

The study adopted the Crumbach's Alpha approach to test the reliability of the instrument. Using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23, Cronbach's alpha test was conducted to check for the internal consistency of the instrument, that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group. Thus, it measured the reliability of the instrument. This approach yielded an index of 0.82 which implies that the instrument was reliable to the tune of 82%.

Administration of Questionnaire

The researcher employed the assistance of 6 youth corps members. 3 are currently serving within Enugu metropolis and 3 in Portharcourt city for easy and quick conclusion of the process. The corpse members were however well orientated and instructed on the administration modalities before they were considered good for the job. This strategy was in order to ensure we worked within the time framework allocated to the exercise. The administration lasted for two weeks. Reminders, calls, discussions, verbal encouragements, were adopted to motivate respondents to volunteer responses and accept questionnaire administration.

Method of Data Analysis

Two methods were adopted for the data analysis. One method consisted in the use of percentage frequencies. The second method was the test of hypothesis using X^2 (chi-square) non-parametric tool given by the statistic:

$$X^2 = \frac{\sum fo - \sum fe}{fe} \quad (2)$$

Where

fo = observed frequency

fe = expected frequency

Decision Rule: = 1f X^2 calculated is $\geq X^2$ table reading, then reject Ho and Accept Ha.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Analysis of Questionnaire Return Rate

This section shows the rate of questionnaire return by the companies sampled. Table 4: presents the outcome of the survey exercise.

Table 4. - Questionnaire Return Rate

<i>TENG/PCNL</i>	<i>No Issued</i>	<i>No Retrieved</i>	<i>AOS</i>	<i>No Issued</i>	<i>No Retrieved</i>	<i>UBA</i>	<i>No Issued</i>	<i>No Retrieved</i>
TENG	35	20	Trans Amadi	24	15	Station Rd.	21	13
PCNL	26	14	OGFZ	21	14	Otigba	17	11
						Gariki	15	7
Total	51	34		45	27		53	31

Total Retrieved | $34 + 27 + 31 = 92$

Table 4. above presents the questionnaire return rate from the different branches of the companies studied. The table shows that the return rate was not quite impressive with a total of 92 questionnaires out of 149 which represents 61.7% return rate. Thus, the final sample size for this study is 92 individuals.

Analysis of Responses to Introductory Questions

In this section, we analyze the responses to the introductory questions of the study.

Figure 2: Gender Composition

Figure 2 Presents the analysis of the gender composition of the study. It shows that 43% of the sample population are males while 57% of them are females.

Figure 3: Marital Status of Respondents

Figure 3 above shows that 59% of them are married, 34.5% of them are single, 0% are divorced while 6.5% of them are separated.

Figure 4: Marital Status of Respondents

Figure 4 show 27% have worked with the firm for a maximum of three years, 33% have worked with their companies for a maximum of 6 years while 40% of them have worked for seven years and above.

On educational qualification presented in figure 5 below, 5.4% of the sample population hold an Ordinary Level certificate in education which is an equivalent of a secondary school education in Nigeria. Another 5.4% possess a master's degree or some higher qualification but 40.2% possess a National Diploma while 49% possess a first degree from a university or its equivalent.

Figure 5: Level of Education of the respondents

Figure 6: Job Status

Of the 92 company's employees included in the survey, 2 persons representing 2.2% of the sample size are in the senior management category, 8 persons representing 8.7% of the sample are in the mid-management cadre, 28 respondents representing 30.4% of them are senior staff members while 54 employees representing 58.7% of the sample size are in the junior staff category.

Figure 7: Level of computer literacy

Finally, on their level of computer literacy represented on the figure above, 11% of the respondents said they possess very high computer knowledge, 35% informed they have high knowledge of computer operations, 38% are moderate while 16% admitted they possess low skills in computer. Nobody admitted that he/she possesses very low knowledge of the computer.

Figure 8: Age Distribution of the Sample

The age bracket of 36-40 holds the modal class of the sample with 26 individuals while the group with the least membership is the group of 51+ with only 4 members.

Analysis of Research Questions

Here, the research questions of the study are analyzed. The section is considered very critical for the objectives of the study to be realized. It looks at the core reasons for the study and separately examines the constituent independent variables of the study to find the pattern of relationship they maintain with the dependent variable of the study.

Research Question 1

How does Records Management affect organizational efficiency?

Table 5: Analysis of Responses to Questions on Research Question 1

	PROPOSITIONS	RESPONSES	NUMBER	%
1.	Adequate documented information (records) management strongly supports the customerism objective	SA	34	37
		A	14	15
		N	-	-
		D	34	37
		SD	10	11
		Total	92	100

2.	It helps to create a positive image of your brand which translates to higher revenue.	SA	28	30
		A	12	13
		N	-	-
		D	35	38
		SD	17	19
	Total	92	100	
3.	Good records management is at the root of quick turnaround time and premium goodwill before your customers.	SA	43	47
		A	22	24
		N	-	-
		D	27	29
		SD	-	-
	Total	92	100	

Table 6: Analysis of Responses to Questions on Research Question 1 (Contd.)

	<i>Propositions</i>	<i>Responses</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
4.	It has a strong positive correlation with profitability.	SA	24	26
		A	15	16
		N	-	-
		D	40	44
		SD	13	14
	Total	92	100	
5.	Good records management has also helped to capture several nitch opportunities for your company.	SA	12	13
		A	20	22
		N	-	-
		D	38	41
		SD	22	24
	Total	92	100	
6.	Adequate documented information management helps in tracking problems and creating solutions for them.	SA	36	39
		A	14	15
		N	-	-
		D	32	35
		SD	10	11
	Total	92	100	
7.	It supports the organization's efforts towards creation of interdepartmental synergy which is necessary for optimal performance and profitability.	SA	28	30
		A	25	27
		N	-	-
		D	22	24
		SD	17	19
	Total	92	100	

Source: Field Survey 2022

In Table 5 and 6 above, the analysis of responses to questions on research question 1 are presented. From the analyses, 52% of the sample agreed to the proposition that adequate documented information (records) management strongly supports the customerism objective while 48% of them disagreed to the proposition.

On the proposition that it helps to create a positive image of your brand which translates to higher revenue, 43% of the sample agreed to the proposition against 57% that disagreed.

71% of the sample affirmed that good records management is at the root of quick turnaround time and premium goodwill before the customers while 29% disagreed to the proposition.

On the question "It has a strong positive correlation with profitability", 42% who answered in agreement to the question against 58% of the sample that answered in disagreement.

35% of the sample agreed that good records management has also helped to capture several niche opportunities for your organization but 65% of the sample expressed disagreement to the proposition.

On the question "Adequate documented information (records) management helps in tracking problems and creating solutions for them", 54% agreement was recorded against 46% disagreement from the respondents.

Similarly, 57% of the respondents agreed to the question that it supports the organization's efforts towards creation of interdepartmental synergy which is necessary for optimal performance and profitability but 43% of the respondents answered in disagreement to the proposition.

Analysis of Research Question 2

To what extent does records management contribute to saving of cost and time of the organization?

Table 7: Analysis of Responses to Questions on Research Question 2

	<i>PROPOSITIONS</i>	<i>RESPONSES</i>	<i>NUMBER</i>	<i>%</i>
8	Good documented information (records) management minimizes time wastage and helps improve overall performance.	SA	32	34
		A	18	20
		N	-	-
		D	20	22
		SD	22	24
		Total	92	100
9	By enhancing turnaround time, records management also helps to minimize cost.	SA	12	13
		A	35	38
		N	-	-
		D	45	49
		SD	-	-
		Total	92	100
10	By reducing cost, it helps to improve overall profitability.	SA	40	44
		A	25	27
		N	-	-
		D	27	29
		SD	-	-
		Total	92	100

Table 8: Analysis of Responses to Questions on Research Question 2 (Contd.)

	<i>Propositions</i>	<i>Responses</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
11	By improving profitability, documented information (records) management enhances returns on investment and market performance of the organization's stocks.	SA	40	43
		A	20	22
		N	-	-

		D	12	13
		SD	20	22
		Total	92	100
12	It helps to strengthen the overall market position of the brand through improved goodwill.	SA	10	11
		A	29	31
		N	-	-
		D	41	45
		SD	12	13
		Total	92	100
13	Documented information (records) management encourages proper allocation of time resources since more tasks are accommodated within a given time frame with good records.	SA	33	36
		A	24	26
		N	-	-
		D	15	16
		SD	20	22
		Total	92	100
14	It is critical to the achievement of the premium market objectives of the firm.	SA	10	11
		A	29	31
		N	-	-
		D	41	45
		SD	12	13
		Total	92	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

Responses to propositions on research question 3 are presented on Table 7 and 8 above.

The table shows that 54% of the responses support the proposition that good documented information (records) management minimizes time wastage and helps improve overall performance, 46% of the responses stand in disagreement to this proposition.

On the question that "By enhancing turnaround time, records management also helps to minimize cost", 51% answered in support against 49% that expressed disagreement.

Out of the total respondents, 71% of the sample respondents agreed that by reducing cost, it helps to improve overall profitability while 29% of them answered in disagreement.

Another 65% of the sample expressed support for the proposition that by improving profitability, records management enhances returns on investment and market performance of the organization's stocks 35% of the responses were in disagreement to this.

Also, 42% of the responses supported the proposition that it helps to strengthen the overall market position of the brand through improved goodwill while 58% of the responses showed disagreement.

Moreso, 62% of the sample answered in support of the proposition that documented information (records) management encourages proper allocation of time resources since more tasks are accommodated within a given time frame with good records while 38% answered in disapproval.

On the question that "It is critical to the achievement of the premium market objectives of the firm", 42% of the respondents showed support against 58% which was in disagreement.

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Test of Hypotheses

Test Statistic

No of Rows = 14, No of columns = 5. Degrees of freedom is 1. Therefore the 5% critical value is:

$$(7-1) \times (5-1) = 6 \times 4 = 24/2 = 12.$$

Checking the value of 12 under 0.05 at the student's "t" statistic table gives 21.0 Therefore our benchmark control value for this test is 21.0 Empirical values of X^2 above 21.0 imply rejection of the null hypothesis while empirical X^2 values below it imply acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Decision Rule:

If X^2 calculated at 5% critical level is $>X^2_{(0.05)}$ tabulated, reject H_0 (that is, accept H_1) and conclude that the variable in question has significant impact on the phenomenon studied. Accept H_0 and conclude otherwise if the reverse is the case.

Test of Hypothesis 1

H_{01} : Records management has no significant impact on organizational efficiency.

Table 8: Summary of Responses for H_{01}

<i>PROPOSITIONS CAPTURING H_{01}</i>	<i>AGREE</i>	<i>DISAGREE</i>	<i>TOTAL</i>
<i>Proposition 1</i>	48	44	92
<i>Proposition 2</i>	40	52	92
<i>Proposition 3</i>	65	27	92
<i>Proposition 4</i>	39	53	92
<i>Proposition 5</i>	32	60	92
<i>Proposition 6</i>	50	42	92
<i>Proposition 7</i>	53	39	92
Total	327	317	644

Table 9. Calculation of cell values for H_{01}

S/N	Calculations for Agreement		Calculations for Disagreement	
1	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
2	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
3	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
4	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
5	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
6	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45

7	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
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Table 10: Table of Contingence for Ho₁

SN	Observed F(O)	Expected F(E)	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E
1	48	47	1	1	0
2	40	47	-7	49	1.0
3	65	47	18	324	6.9
4	39	47	-8	64	1.4
5	32	47	-15	225	4.8
6	50	47	3	9	0.2
7	53	47	6	36	0.8
8	44	45	-1	1	0
9	52	45	7	49	1.2
10	27	45	18	324	7.2
11	53	45	8	64	1.4
12	60	45	15	225	5
13	42	45	-3	9	0.2
14	39	45	-6	36	0.8
<i>X² Calculated</i>					30.9

Since our empirical X² calculated at 5% critical level is 30.9 which is > X² tabulated (21.0), we Accept H₁ (that is, Reject H₀) and conclude that records management has significant impact on organizational efficiency.

Test of Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: Records management does not significantly contribute toward saving of cost and time of the organization.

Table 11: Summary of Responses for Ho₃

PROPOSITIONS CAPTURING HO1	AGREE	DISAGREE	TOTAL
Proposition 15	50	42	92
Proposition 16	47	45	92
Proposition 17	65	27	92
Proposition 18	60	32	92
Proposition 19	39	53	92
Proposition 20	57	35	92
Proposition 21	39	53	92
Total	357	287	644

Table 12 Calculation of cell values for Ho₃

S/N	Calculations for Agreement	Calculations for Disagreement
1	$\frac{357 \times 92}{644}$	$\frac{287 \times 92}{644}$

	644		644	
2	$\frac{357 \times 92}{644}$	51	$\frac{287 \times 92}{644}$	41
3	$\frac{357 \times 92}{644}$	51	$\frac{287 \times 92}{644}$	41
4	$\frac{357 \times 92}{644}$	51	$\frac{287 \times 92}{644}$	41
5	$\frac{357 \times 92}{644}$	51	$\frac{287 \times 92}{644}$	41
6	$\frac{357 \times 92}{644}$	51	$\frac{287 \times 92}{644}$	41
7	$\frac{357 \times 92}{644}$	51	$\frac{287 \times 92}{644}$	41

Table 12: Table of Contingence for Ho₁

	Observed F (O)	Expected F (E)	O-E	(O-E) ²	$\frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
1	50	51	-1	1	0
2	47	51	-4	16	0.3
3	65	51	14	196	3.8
4	60	51	9	81	1.6
5	39	51	-12	144	2.8
6	57	51	6	36	0.7
7	39	51	-12	144	2.8
8	42	41	1	1	0
9	45	41	4	16	0.4
10	27	41	-14	196	4.9
11	32	41	-9	81	2
12	53	41	12	144	3.5
13	35	41	-6	36	0.9
14	53	41	12	144	3.5
				<i>X² Calculated</i>	27.2

Conclusion

Since our empirical X^2 calculated at 5% critical level is 27.2 which is $> X^2$ tabulated (21.0), we again Reject H_0 (that is, accept H_1) and conclude that records management does significantly contribute toward saving of cost and time of the organization.

Summary of Findings

1. The study found a significant impact on proper records keeping and documented information management on organizational efficiency. The empirical Chi-square value reached by the study was 30.9 against the statistical table reading at the 5% critical level of 21.0. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis for the test.
2. Again, the study reached an observed Chi-square value of 27.2 against the same benchmark statistical table reading of 21.0 which also implied rejection of the null hypothesis.

In both tests, we note that efficiency of the organization was proxied by profitability, reduction in time wastage and saving of cost.

Conclusion

From these findings and from the studies reviewed, the critical position of records and documented information management to competitive organizational performance was strongly felt. The tests conducted supported the view that records keeping, and management significantly impacts organizational efficiency. This finding resonates with the views of the studies reviewed under the extant literature analysis. It was found that all the studies pointed to the importance of documented information to efficient organizational performance. Of course, it is easy to see how difficult execution of tasks would be without resort to documented information as a guide to proper processes in the execution. Scholars agree that was found that with proper records management, it is easy to strategize on what to do, how to do it and for whom to do it. Client management is enabled by resort to critical information resources. Correction of erroneous procedures is enabled by records, financial planning, training and adaptation planning are aided by records and general work strategies are supported by records. Thus, existing literature in the area has argued strongly in support of the utility value of proper records and information management in the process of job implementation and strategy development for competitive performance.

Recommendations

- i. There should be overall regulatory framework in the country for proper records management at all organizational levels and functions.
- ii. Organizations should also have a consistent dossier of policies guiding records management to ensure easy access to vital information and retention of corporate memory.
- iii. Information management managers should be technically trained on their jobs.
- iv. Filing of records should follow a properly indexed method for ease of identification, retrieval and utilization by every member of the organization.
- v. Organizations should incorporate modern techniques of information management such as integrated document management. Digital corporate memory files should be kept and modern technology should be generously employed in records management.
- vi. There should be sufficient budgets for the records management system to ensure they are well resourced to function optimally.
- vii. Supervision and Control should be exerted in all records management processes. There should be proper supervision to enable records managers keep effective records in the organization and the management must take control of records management to secure the integrity of records. Standards need to be set; actual result need to be measured; and deviations need to be corrected immediately.

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